

Emerging phenomena in quantised space

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In classic physics phenomena are distinguishable by their properties. Actually a phenomenon is the “unthreatened owner” of its properties. Nowadays these ideas are more nuanced. This paper dives with the help of the model of quantised space into the underlying reality that creates the emergence of phenomena.

Introduction

Phenomenological reality is relational reality.^[1] The consequence is that relational reality manifests itself with the help of transformations. At least if we suppose that our universe represents one enormous all-inclusive system that is ruled by conservation laws (invariance of at least one basic property). The term *transformation* suggests that the phenomenon is part of an all-inclusive creating reality. Actually the properties of the phenomenon are the result of a underlying causation. In line with the existence of universal conservation laws in relation to energy and momentum. Although the term *emergence* suggests a more diffuse concept, in practice its meaning shows to be quite [similar](#).

The model of quantised space^{[2][3]} represents a point of view about the nature of reality that originates from the ancient Greek philosopher and mathematician Parmenides of Elea (about 500 B.C.). He was convinced that relational reality is created by an underlying ontological reality that exists everywhere in the universe (emptiness doesn't exist). In other words, the underlying reality is the rest frame that creates relational reality. The consequence is that the underlying reality will “come to life” as a non-observable (dynamical) mathematical construct.

References:

1. S.E. Grimm (2025); “*The non-observable universe*” Page 1 – 4. <https://zenodo.org/records/15387290>
2. S.E. Grimm (2020); “*On the construction of the properties of discrete space*” <https://zenodo.org/records/3909268>
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Basic quantum fields

Relational reality is what we observe and what we can measure. So it is obvious that we ask ourselves if we can observe and measure space and time itself. The answer is negative. We cannot measure space and time, because we can only observe and measure mutual relations. We only know that time reflects change and space is the experience of volume.

Besides all the tangible phenomena, we also observe and measure influences that exist in between the tangible phenomena. In physics these influences are termed (force) *fields*. However, with the help of Parmenides ontological concept of reality it is clear that the volume of the universe at the smallest scale size has distinct basic mathematical properties. Like the discreteness and invariance of the volume of the universe, the existence of scalars (spherical shape), fluent transformation of 3D shapes (topological spaces) and instantaneous action (vectors).

In physics these mathematical properties are described as field properties. Basic (quantum) fields that are known as the Higgs field, the electric field and its corresponding magnetic field. The last 2 fields together are termed *electromagnetic field* in modern physics. Each field represents a different singular mathematical property. Unfortunately, this is not the consensus in theoretical physics, because physics is based on the scientific method. Therefore it is not uncommon that theorists hypothesise the existence of multiple fields with the same mathematical properties (like multiple scalar fields). Because the scientific method is not a model or a universal concept, it is an opinion how we have to organise physical science to get reliable results. It is obvious that the scientific method is not well suited to determine the underlying nature of relational reality.

The hypotheses that the universe is tessellated with basic quantum fields doesn't contradict Parmenides' ontological concept of reality. Although it is clear that we have to reinterpret our concept of (force) fields. Simply because in modern physics we interpret the basic quantum fields as a type of phenomena, like particles and forces. But if basic quantum fields are phenomena in relational reality the speed of light cannot be a constant and the quantum of

energy cannot have a universal fixed quantity. Especially if we combine these facts with the unhinged idea that all the basic quantum fields originate from one singular point “in empty space” some 13,7 billions years in the past.

If we interpret the basic quantum fields as a detailed addition to the general description of Parmenides’ concept, the picture becomes more reasonable. Because the idea has the benefit that it couples relational reality with the underlying creating reality. In other words, the properties of the basic quantum fields represent the mutual differences between the units of the 3D metric of the universe (quantised space). The consequence is that every unit of quantised space will manifest the properties of the 3 basic quantum fields. Thus every unit of quantised space represents a scalar, a vector and the topological deformation of its shape.

The existence of the hypothetical 3D metric of quantised space – in line with the concept of Parmenides of Elea – emerges from the Planck-Einstein relation:

$$E = h \nu = h \frac{c}{\lambda} \quad \rightarrow \quad h \frac{c}{n \ell_c}$$

[h = the Planck constant; ν = frequency; c = speed of light; λ = wave length; n = integer; ℓ_c = metric]

In theoretical physics the wave length (λ) is thought to be the only variable in the Planck-Einstein relation. But this is theoretically impossible in an equation with only universal constants (h ; c). In other words, the wave length (λ) of an electromagnetic wave represents the universal constant of length (ℓ_c) or its multiple ($n \ell_c$).

Emergence

It is clear that there exists a 3D metric in our universe and it can be described as a quantisation of the whole volume of the universe. Moreover, these units of quantised space will have identical basic properties otherwise our universe cannot transform on and on. Not at least because in relational reality the universe shows itself to us as a dynamical continuum.^[4]

The dynamics that is responsible for the transformation of all the units of quantised space is the internal spherical shape forming mechanism (scalar mechanism). Its existence is undeniable because in relational reality the spherical shape is the dominant shape everywhere in our universe. Therefore it is reasonable to conclude that every unit must reflect this spherical shape forming mechanism.

The conclusion has consequences because it implies that the continuous transformation of the properties of the units of quantised space – determined with the help of the observable and detectable phenomena in relational reality – doesn’t originate from an external influence. It is the universe itself that generates all the dynamics.

But a volume with a structure that is build up by units with identical basic properties shows a high amount of similarity with a 3D [fractal](#) (mathematics).^[5] More realistic: in mathematics we have discovered fractals because fractals – like set theory^[4] – represent general properties of the underlying creating reality.

So we have to conclude that relational reality – that is the [subject](#) physicists explore – emerges from the underlying creating reality of the universe itself. A set of units with identical basic properties that tessellate the mathematical volume of the universe.

References:

4. S.E. Grimm (2019); “*Empiricism and empirical information*”
<https://zenodo.org/records/3592378>
5. S.E. Grimm (2019); “*The objective reality of space and time*”
<https://zenodo.org/records/3593872>

Conclusion

In ancient Greece “natural” philosophers tried to understand the nature of relational reality. The famous mathematician and philosopher Parmenides of Elea solved this query some 2500 years ago. Parmenides ideas were not unknown in ancient Greece because the concept can also be found in Plato’s work about the Republic (the [allegory of the cave](#)). Unfortunately, most people are heavily blinded by the urge to interpret the mutual relations between the phenomena in relational reality. Besides that, most of the work of Parmenides and his students (e.g. Zeno of Elea) is lost.

So it is a bit ironic that physicists are trying to find the [theory of everything](#) while the ancient Greek mathematician and philosopher Parmenides of Elea already described the consistent concept two and a half millennia ago. Fortunately modern physics have obtained so much details about relational reality that it is easier nowadays to verify the existence of the underlying creating reality. Inclusive the origin of consciousness.